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Microservices Design of Notification, Dashboard and Reconciliation System

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Abstract

Implementations of the policy book creation integration system have 99.98 % Success Rate. But, there is still a 32.65 % transaction higher than average transaction time. The design of notification, reconciliation and dashboard systems is expected to provide solutions to maximize system capabilities. Using existing architecture which is micro services, services and using services that available to call. Development using java spring framework expected to make development easier and faster.

1. Introduction

Development of policy book creation integration system on insurance company have been done and implemented for 1 year. Since January 2018 some information could extracted. And the result shows that 99.98% transaction is success [2]. But, unfortunately 32.65% transaction still higher than average, average transaction time is 27.66 second. Apart from transaction record, there is also information that some of transaction is suspended on business user side. Highest transaction time is 310 Days, so far from average.

Issues like this if the executive not reported to the executive, because this is out of expectation and promise of the company to customers and agents. The indifference of negative result on the system is because of the percentage of a successful transaction.

This condition needs to address by another system to solve this kind of issues. Delivering information to stack holder can be done by giving them access to that information as the dashboard, notification of information to some failure transaction that passed system threshold, and reconciliation system that can make sure all transaction is done by the expected time.

2. Design process flow

The flow of integration [1] system such as:

Fig. 1 process flow

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Image 1 explains that after scheduler triggers the system, there is at least 12 step until it stopped. To give business user visibility of the situation of system, error code/message should be generated and passed to them, fortunately, policy book creation integration system has that.

3. Design of Dashboard

Using a transaction log of policy book creation integration system. Data on the dashboard will show information on open, ongoing, failed, and successful transaction. The open transaction is a transaction on waiting before is started. On progress, the transaction is a transaction that processed in the system. The failed transaction is a transaction that failed system process. Success transaction is a transaction that already passed the system process and successfully integrates to correspondence system.

Transaction log already has some status that separates into for status OPEN, ON_PROGRESS, SUCCESS and FAILED. All status can be shown to help stack holder to start to investigate if a lot of transaction failing the process. Some diagram can choose to visualize system status, such as:

Fig. 2 Diagram Pie

Diagram pie like on image 2 is illustrated to shows system status.

4. Notification

After having a dashboard, high level management has visibility to see system status and easy to see what is going on. But for the business user, who runs it with the problem inside the system that information does not enough.

So that there is a needs to build a notification system that reaches business user on their daily activity. The notification system will have configuration about, level one user, level two user and etc. It will set by user needs. Other than leveling user notification, the notification system will process by schedule every ten minutes. Notification system with escalation feature expected to increase stack holder productivity. This notification system should be adjusted to stack holder audience, because stack holder to this system not only IT Team but also business user, so that person who gets this notification can solve the issues and not mislead.

IT Team will solve issues if any services that support the integration system is down and not accessible. Meanwhile, the business user will solve the issue related to data completeness and unsupported format.

This notification will use an existing feature of notification like email and short message service (SMS). This kind of integration doesn't need any development because already available on services catalog of the company.

An email will have a short explanation of an unsuccessful transaction. Information like policy number, transaction time and an error message will fill the email. For SMS format, it will remember business user, that there is a transaction that failing the process.

5. Reconciliation

Reconciliation becomes important for ensuring that the system has good build quality. Reconciliation needs some input that data should come from the core system, correspondence system, and integration system. Every system has a different format, but every system have policy number as an input so that reconciliation can do it works, Reconciliation should do first thing in the morning because this is an internal system. All process could be automated and the business user can see the result.

6. Microservices Design Pattern

Reusability of the resource should do to minimize time consuming of developing the system. Like a notification system that will use existing notification services to send email and SMS.

For development, this notification system spring framework is a choice of framework to build the system. Spring framework already trusted by the company to make the developer have standard when doing their program. Besides that, the spring framework has feature spring-boot and spring cloud used by the company to revolutionized its development standard.

To make development easier there is some list of the library that commonly used by some services on the company, such as:

1. [spring-boot-starter-parent](#)
2. [spring-cloud-starter-config](#)
3. [spring-boot-starter-data-jpa](#)
4. [spring-boot-starter-data-rest](#)
5. [spring-boot-starter-web](#)
6. [springfox-swagger2](#)
7. [springfox-swagger-ui](#)
8. [springfox-data-rest](#)

All of the modules above already used by some of the company projects and so far no big issues for using this pattern. With this pattern development expected to be faster for starting to develop, because they do not need to research.

7. Conclusion

System dashboard is needed for sure, but that is not enough for all stack holder. Some stack holder needs more detail information that dashboard can show up. So, the notification system can give that kind information to solve this kind of needs. Reconciliation will ensure daily transaction so that user have recorded how many transactions pending day by day. Reusing existing services will make development is faster. And with a standardized library, a developer can start faster and hopefully the system can be delivered to the business user faster.

References

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